

Multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and activism: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations?¹

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Concepts employed to capture certain language phenomena are often intended to depict and reflect real-world occurrences of such phenomena. Rarely ever does the intentionality of doing so entail capturing linguistic and sociolinguistic misrepresentations. In some instances, linguistic and sociolinguistic representations are one thing; in other instances, they can result in misrepresentations. This conceptual paper uses South Africa as its main point of reference. Against this backdrop, the paper explores the nexus between multilingualism, translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism in the South African context. Firstly, it contends that even though translanguaging is often framed differentially from multilingualism, the latter, nevertheless, serves as its alter ego, its point of reference, and its nemesis. Secondly, it argues that both multilingualism and translanguaging, as transformative vehicles for realising human rights-centric goals such as diversity, equity, and social justice, and as efforts for challenging and dismantling the hegemony of English or Anglonormativity in South Africa, are inherently constrained and hamstrung. Thirdly, it unpacks the myth about multilingualism and translanguaging in South Africa. Fourthly and lastly, it highlights the conundrum of South Africa's multilingualism.

Keywords: Diversity; Equity; Language Activism; Multilingualism; Social Justice; Translanguaging

1. Introduction

There are instances when multilingualism and translanguaging are linked to any one or more of the following concepts: diversity, equity, social justice, and activism. When this happens, the idea is that using or applying one of them in real-world contexts signals and embodies a semblance of diversity, equity, social justice, or activism. Underscoring this practice is the belief (implicit or explicit) that doing so entails enacting any one or more of these four concepts simultaneously. Nevertheless, there are, and there have been, cases where reference is made to (a) linguistic diversity, (b) linguistic equity, (c) linguistic social justice, or (d) linguistic activism. Mostly, these concepts are appropriated and invoked in relation to marginalised, peripheral, or subaltern

languages such as indigenous or minoritised languages and, in some cases, with reference to majoritised languages, especially, in sociolinguistic contexts in which such languages exist alongside one or more dominant languages.

While this is not the sole reason, languages become marginalised or peripheral when one or more languages, particularly, former colonial, nation-state languages such as English, French, Portuguese, or Spanish tend to assume a hegemonic, unchallengeable, and monopolistic role in key domains of use in a given language setup. Africa is teeming with such linguistic contexts: contexts in which majoritised indigenous or local languages are marginalised despite their having majority mother-tongue speakers. In these contexts, the use and invocation of any of the four concepts mentioned above does make a language sense, even though not necessarily a sociolinguistic sense. The latter sense throws a spanner in the invocation works of any of these four concepts as their linguistic invocations do not always lead to language transformation, or to a fair and equal language-playing field. Neither do their invocations, at times, result in challenging and dismantling the hegemony of English or Anglonormativity, especially in the South African context. On this basis, the paper uses South Africa as a reference point to frame both its arguments and its discussion.

2. Overview of major concepts

Both multilingualism and translanguaging as concepts need no explication as there are a lot of scholarly articles and books that have defined and unpacked them (Cenoz & Gorter, 2019; Charamba & Nkomo, 2022; Childs, 2016; García & Alvis, 2019; Han, 2022; Jaspers, 2018; Léglise, 2017; Leung & Valdés, 2019; Ticheloven et al., 2019; Wilson, 2021). There are even scholars who have, in a way, problematised them (Brooks, 2022; Chaka, 2023a; Cummins, 2021; Jaspers, 2018; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2020). The two concepts have also had their application and use in certain contexts contested and questioned, particularly due to their sometimes definitional slipperiness and convolution (Brooks, 2022; Chaka, 2020, 2023a, 2023b; Cummins, 2021; Heugh, 2021; Jaspers, 2018; Singleton & Flynn, 2021).

Needless to say, they do not mean the same thing. For instance, neither of these terms carries the same connotations when applied to Northern metropolises such as the United States (i.e., the US) and the United Kingdom (i.e., the UK) as when applied to Southern contexts like Africa, and South and Southeast Asia. In the former case, bilingual situations comprise mainly English (as a majority language) and minoritised languages. In the latter case, multilingual situations consist of local languages as majority languages relative to English or to any other former colonial language (Chaka, 2023a; Chaka & Ndlangamandla, 2023; Heugh, 2021).

So, Euro-American multilingualism and translanguaging are not necessarily the same as multilingualism and translanguaging as used in African, and South and Southeast Asian contexts. This is one of the reasons, especially in relation to multilingualism, that this term, at times, gets pluralised, and has given rise to differentiating references like Northern multilingualisms and Southern multilingualisms (Chaka & Ndlangamandla, 2023; Heugh, 2021; Makoni & Severo, 2022; Pennycook & Makoni, 2020). Elsewhere, Chaka and Ndlangamandla (2023) even talk of the sociolinguistic *isms of the Souths* to try and capture the multiple multilingualisms characteristic of the Souths, wherein the Souths, in lieu of the Global South, is a preferred term to foreground both the many and varied regions comprising the Global South and the diverse and multiple populations and peoples inhabiting these global regions (also see Chaka, 2022). A parallel to Northern multilingualisms and Southern multilingualisms is Northern translanguaging and Southern translanguaging, a process which has not yet gained currency, despite its obviousness.

While multilingualism appears to be self-explanatory, depending, of course, on the global context in which it is used as highlighted above, even though it sometimes tends to be conflated with bilingualism, the same does not hold for translanguaging. Since its original conceptualisation when it was used in a Welsh-English bilingual classroom pedagogical context, translanguaging has mutated, and has had its meaning extended. It now has multiple references—i.e., ‘affordances’ à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021)—as it:

- refers to the natural language instinct and the innate cognitive capacity speakers possess (García & Li, 2014);
- signals the psychological or mental awareness speakers, multilingual or otherwise, have of their own linguistic competences (Ortheguy et al., 2015);
- entails language practices, inherently discursively multiple and fluid, that speakers use to navigate their own worlds (García & Li, 2014; García et al., 2015; Makalela, 2015);
- involves the act of performing by speakers to access and use diverse linguistic features available in their own, equally diverse, linguistic repertoires, irrespective of the boundaries imposed by named languages (García, 2009);
- is an approach to language use and language education (Charamba & Nkomo, 2022; Childs, 2016; De los Ríos & Seltzer, 2017; Donley, 2022; Han, 2022; Hurst & Mona, 2017; Vaish, 2018);
- is a theory of language (Donley, 2022; Liu & Fang, 2022; García & Kleyn, 2016; Marrero-Colón, 2022); and

- is a strategy to achieve linguistic equity and diversity, language transformation and decolonisation (Donley, 2022; García & Alvis, 2019; García & Leiva, 2014; García & Li, 2014; Wang, 2022a).

Jaspers (2018) flags these multiple meanings of translanguaging in varying degrees (also see Chaka, 2020, 2023a, 2023b; Cummins, 2021; Poza, 2017). One of the major concerns, in this regard, is that, when a revolutionary and innovative concept that was formulated under specific classroom contexts—which Salmani Nodoushan (2023) has referred to as a ‘petri dish’ or a ‘panopticon’—to achieve a specific purpose, incessantly tends to be endowed with multiple meanings—or ‘injected senses’ à la Salmani Nodoushan (2022)—and is endlessly expected to serve multiple purposes, it runs the risk of losing its founding principle (Chaka, 2023a). When that happens, and when no halt is made to its ever-evolving meanings and purposes, it will end up being a diluted and questionable concept that it should not be. For example, if I can venture to say that for me translanguaging is the science of languaging, it is the physics of applying diverse, fluid, multiple linguistic repertoires and multiple linguistic competences by those who want to defy the gravity exerted by, and the omniscience of, Western, colonial, normative, nation-state, named languages on indigenous, peripheral, and subaltern languages, who can judge me wrong or irrelevant? All I need to do is provide relevant, tangible, and bespoke translanguaging evidence to back up my science and physics claims. But, already, I have made an assertion to that effect. Opining about the ever-expanding uses of translanguaging, Jaspers (2017) cautions that doing so is a huge ask for this concept as it is likely to lose what it signifies (also see Eagleton, 1994). I struggle to disagree with this caveat. Translanguaging cannot mean anything that anyone desires it to mean. If that happens, then, we are likely to be groping in a semantic minefield in which, words we use, à la Humpty Dumpty, would mean what we choose them to mean (Carroll, 1971; Chaka, 2023a). We need to take leaf out of words such as *ideology*, *discourse*, *power* (Chaka, 2006) and, recently, *narrative*, and ensure that translanguaging, as an aptly revolutionary and innovative concept, does not go the route of these four words (Chaka, 2023a).

Mostly, translanguaging is framed differentially from multilingualism, which is its alter ego, its point of reference, and its nemesis. It is its alter ego since when it is invoked, multilingualism is also invoked. For the same reason, multilingualism is its reference point, whether in a like or in an unlike manner. In fact, it is uncommon to come across an instance where translanguaging is mentioned without multilingualism being mentioned as well. It is its nemesis because most translanguaging scholars are averse to being seen as multilingualism scholars, or to being seen as advocates of multilingualism when they talk about translanguaging.

Often, both multilingualism and translanguaging are associated with, and are seen as, vehicles for promoting diversity, equity, and social justice. This is even more so with translanguaging (see, for example, Csata & Marácz, 2021; Heugh et al., 2022; Skutnabb-Kangas et al., 2009; Parra & Proctor, 2022; Shohamy, 2022; Tai, 2021; Veliz, 2021; Wang, 2022b; Yilmaz, 2019). When both of these terms are appropriated and invoked in this sense, it is expected that they can even equalise or rebalance the language disequilibrium existing in given sociolinguistic setups obtaining in different countries. This is particularly so since in this sense, over and above their being vehicles for diversity, equity, and social justice, they also become proxies for these three concepts. The other expectation is that they can serve as tools for linguistic transformation and decolonisation. In language studies, the notion of linguistic diversity embodies linguistic heterogeneity or multilingualism itself (Léglise, 2017; Piller, 2021; Randolph, Jr. & Johnson, 2017; Wang, 2022b). Largely, diversity is a politically correct reference to the now-maligned twin concepts, *multiculturalism* and *multiracialism*. Linguistic equity is a poster reference to language equality or to equality of languages, whose main conduits are multilingualism and translanguaging, especially for racialised, marginalised, and minoritised language speakers/groups. For its part, social justice is about ensuring that there is a measure of fairness and justice across diverse social groups. From it is derived linguistic justice, which has to do with guaranteeing linguistic fairness and justice among different languages, which are, mostly, characterised by skewed linguistic asymmetries and hierarchies. As UNESCO (2022) argues, the concept of *social justice* consists of a wide-ranging canvas that includes, but not exclusively, race, racism, inequality, xenophobia, homophobia, misogyny, gender, ableism, land, the environment, property, wealth, and economic discrimination. However, in this paper, social justice is appropriated relative to linguistic justice and with reference to the implications it has for linguistic justice.

All the three aforementioned terms (diversity, equity, and social justice) often co-occur. Crucially, they have a university-level module status in eponymous courses such as equity, diversity, and social justice courses (see Ankomah, 2020), which are particularly offered at some of North American universities, mainly, under the equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) banner. This includes centres or offices that bear the same composite name. In this context, they are part of inclusive education, which, in the case of language studies and language education, is intended to embrace and affirm diversity and equity of, and social justice for languages through multilingualism and translanguaging as the main conduits for realising and enacting them. These three terms also have a human rights and, particularly a language rights, orientation which is not necessarily new (see, for example, Rojas & Reagan, 2003; Skutnabb-Kanga et al., 1994; Skutnabb-Kangas et al., 2009). Embracing and invoking these three terms,

additionally, reflects elements of critical pedagogy. The latter is grounded in Freirean critical pedagogy (cf. Salmani Nodoushan & Daftarifard, 2011), three tenets of which are critical consciousness (*conscientization*), literacy (language) and power, and the view of curricula and schools as points of resistance and as agents of transformation (Freire, 1970, 2005; Jaspers, 2018; Randolph, Jr. & Johnson, 2017).

On this basis, multilingualism and translanguaging are seen as conduits for linguistic transformation and decolonisation as they embody linguistic diversity, equity, and justice, or because they serve as proxies for these three terms. The application of critical pedagogy to language is not new, nor is it exclusive to multilingualism and translanguaging. There are previous instances of it in Fowler and Kress's (1979) critical linguistics, in Fairclough's (1989) *Language and Power* (also see Chaka, 2006), and in Pennycook's (2001) critical applied linguistics.

Lastly, language activism is actively campaigning for the use, promotion, revitalisation, and preservation of, especially, albeit not exclusively, marginalised indigenous or minoritised languages. Activism, in this case, is a conscious, unrelenting, energetic, ongoing, and sustainable endeavour. It may be ideologically or theoretically driven (see Combs & Penfield, 2012; Pierite & Davis, 2022), or community-driven. It is an action or a practice that can be brought to bear on multilingualism and translanguaging in order to advocate and promote linguistic diversity, equity, and justice.

3. The South African context

In this section, I use instances of the South African language and sociolinguistic scenario to elucidate and interrogate some of the points highlighted above about multilingualism and translanguaging in relation to diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism.

South Africa has eleven official languages, a point tritely expressed by different scholars (see, for example, Cele, 2021; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022; Ngoepe, 2020). These official languages consist of nine African languages—isiNdebele, Sepedi, Sesotho, Setswana, isiSwati, Tshivenda, Xitsonga, isiXhosa, and isiZulu—on the one hand, and of Afrikaans and English, on the other hand. In spite of the fact that the eleven languages are legislatively officialised, English remains a privileged and dominant language in almost all the critical usage domains, including most government structures (the three arms of government and government departments), in the country. Not only that, but that English is also the main, if not the sole, language of learning and teaching (LoLT) at both school and university levels, barring a few instances in which Afrikaans serves as a LoLT, or except for instances where it (Afrikaans) serves as a dual LoLT with English (Chaka et al., 2022; Ndlangamandla & Chaka, 2022).

At a provincial level, each of South Africa's nine provinces has its own official languages, which, mainly, consist of one African language or more of the African languages together with English or Afrikaans, depending on a given province's demographics. Nevertheless, as is the case with the national level language scenario, English is still a preferred language for primary usage domains and, again, serves as the main LoLT at provincial levels as well, except for limited instances in which Afrikaans does so or does so in tandem with English (Chaka & Ndlangamandla, 2023; cf. South Africa Gateway, 2021, 2022).

The main provincial languages, for each province, are mapped as follows, with provinces' names featured alphabetically:

- Eastern Cape (Three main languages: isiXhosa = 82,7%; Afrikaans = 10,3%; English = 3,9%)
- Free State (Three main languages: Sesotho = 71,9%; Afrikaans = 10,9%; isiXhosa = 5,7%)
- Gauteng (Four main languages: IsiZulu = 23,0%; Afrikaans = 10,1%; Sesotho = 12,7%; English = 11,3%)
- KwaZulu-Natal (Three main languages: isiZulu = 82,5%; English = 12,5%; Afrikaans = 1,0%)
- Limpopo (Three main languages: Sepedi = 56,0%; Tshivenda = 17,1%; Xitsonga = 16,6%)
- Mpumalanga (Four main languages: isiSwati = 29,1%; isiZulu = 28,8%; Xitsonga = 9,6%; isiNdebele = 10,1%)
- Northern Cape (Two main languages: Afrikaans = 56,8%; Setswana = 33,4%)
- North West (Three main languages: Setswana = 71,5%; Afrikaans = 8,96%; isiXhosa = 5,51%)
- Western Cape (Three main languages: Afrikaans = 46,6%; isiXhosa = 31,1%; English = 19,6%) (South Africa Year Book 2022/22, 2021-2022; Stats SA, 2022).

Against the provincial language background provided above, the paper argues that multilingualism and translanguaging are seen as tools that can challenge the hegemony of English or Anglonormativity (Beiler, 2023; McKinney, 2017; also see Chaka, 2021, 2023a, 2023b), and that can also engender linguistic diversity, equity, and justice in the South African context (see Chaka et al., 2022; Charamba & Nkomo, 2022; Childs, 2016; Hurst & Mona, 2017; Stroud & Kerfoot, 2021). This view is particularly predominant within South Africa's

educational contexts—both at school and university levels—where multilingualism and translanguaging are not only regarded as tools for linguistic diversity, equity, and justice, but are seen as pedagogical approaches for enabling epistemic access for students as well (Chaka, 2020; Charamba & Nkomo, 2022; Hurst & Mona, 2017; Makalela, 2015; Mbirimi-Hungwe, 2018; Probyn, 2019). The paper argues that while school- and university-based applications of multilingualism and translanguaging, which are largely classroom-based or which are mainly directed to selected groups of students, might have good intentions for challenging Anglonormativity, and for promoting linguistic diversity, equity, and justice, they are inherently and structurally constrictive. That is, their impact, if any, is mostly confined to the given classrooms and to the selected groups of students for which they meant. Therefore, their linguistic diversity, equity, and justice efforts have no wider reach as they are limited to these specified confines. And, the dent they are intended to make in neutralising Anglonormativity is equally constrained. In this case, these efforts are, at best, idealistic, or, at worst, tokenistic. Allied to the first argument is that most of these multilingual and translanguaging endeavours lack continuity. The point, here, is that they are one-off, standalone efforts that do not continue beyond their school or university application contexts, or that do not flow over from schools to universities once they commence at school levels. Again, coupled with this is the fact that there is a lack of large-scale, longitudinal studies that can prove that the success of multilingual and translanguaging endeavours in challenging Anglonormativity, and in promoting linguistic diversity, equity, and justice in one classroom/school context can do so in other classroom/school contexts, or that multilingual and translanguaging endeavours that are applied in a selected student group context at one university can succeed in other selected student group contexts at other universities.

Another argument that the paper makes is that classroom multilingual and translanguaging practices at any school/university context may, at times, be influenced by the main African languages spoken at provincial levels, especially the ones that are majority languages at given provinces. For example, according to the provincial languages mapped earlier, in the case of Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Free State, and North West, isiXhosa (82,7%), isiZulu (82,5%), Sesotho (71,9%), and Setswana (71,5%) (South Africa Year Book 2022/22, 2021-2022; Stats SA, 2022) are, respectively, almost absolute majority languages in these provinces. In this regard, the enthusiasm of majoritised language speakers to embrace multilingual and translanguaging practices in classroom situations is, I surmise, likely to be very low. This point speaks to language attitudes that majority African language speakers have toward other minoritised African languages (Chauke, 2020; Manganyi, 1997) in order for multilingual and translanguaging practices to occur. And, it is one

central issue that advocates and practitioners of multilingualism and translanguaging need to note to avoid essentialising classroom-based multilingual and translanguaging approaches, and presenting them romantically and unproblematically (see Chaka, 2023a).

Additionally, it will take more than multilingual and translanguaging approaches to challenge and dismantle the hegemony of English within educational contexts and in public domains in South Africa. For instance, in the main provincial languages portrayed above, English has a tiny foothold as one of the main languages, albeit in incremental degrees, in three provinces (e.g., Eastern Cape = 3,9%, Gauteng = 11,3%, and Western Cape = 19,6%). But, it does not feature as one of the other main provincial languages in the other provinces, at least, according to the data provided by the specified government agencies cited earlier. However, it has an almost monopolistic hegemony as a LoLT and in public domains in all the nine provinces as mentioned earlier. This is due to colonialingual practices (Chaka & Ndlangamandla, 2023; also see Meighan, 2022, 2023) obtaining in South Africa, post its independence, one of which is that English, as a former colonial language, is privileged over indigenous African languages, notwithstanding that they, too, are official languages and are majority languages in all provinces, bar two. This colonialingual tendency tends to highlight how English, as an instance of Anglonormativity, continues to be weaponised against indigenous African languages in South Africa. So, irrespective of the main provincial languages mapped above, the stronghold English has in South Africa cannot be unhinged by multilingualism and translanguaging alone. All colonialingual practices and other structural colonialist or neocolonial tendencies have to be addressed, not only by academics and scholars alone, but by the government as well.

The paper further argues that the apparent indifference, or ambivalence, that some of the university managers and planners display to, and a lack of language activism they have for multilingualism and translanguaging, is unhelpful. It is one of the stumbling blocks to the implementation of this dual pedagogical approach: the approach does not have most university managements' buy-in. As such, it simply becomes a scholarly need (or even a pastime) for a few concerned academics. This is where language activism is missing. Our university managers, most of whom these days are speakers of some of the African languages, do not seem to show and display the activism that multilingualism and translanguaging scholars and practitioners tend to show and display. One can hazard to say that they do not have a burning passion for their own languages to be used as LoLTs, and to be used as languages of research, scholarship, knowledge, science, technology, and development, even if this were to be in some distant future.

Another concern is that most of the initiatives about, and most of the debates on, multilingualism and translanguaging tend to be confined to academia, especially to higher education institutions (HEIs) (see Chaka, 2023a; Mbirimi-Hungwe, 2018; Mkhize & Balfour, 2017; Motaung, 2021; Probyn, 2019). Much does not seem to be the case with schools, a sector that feeds into HEIs. This apparent lack of multilingualism and translanguaging initiatives and debates at school level (cf. Childs, 2016) means that a bottom-up approach to multilingualism and translanguaging in education is currently missing in South Africa.

Furthermore, the myth about multilingualism and translanguaging in South Africa needs some unpacking. Given the distribution of the main provincial languages plotted earlier, and taking into account their relative confinement to certain provinces, and how some languages feature in some provinces and not in others, one wonders how, sociolinguistically speaking, South Africa is often branded a multilingual country. At best, it is a country with six trilingual-majority provinces, two quadrilingual-majority provinces, and one bilingual-majority province. Of course, one can contend, maybe rightly so, that Gauteng is always touted as a multilingual province, or as a cauldron of multilingualism in South Africa. Maybe it is as other African languages spoken, especially in both the Johannesburg Metropolitan City and the Tshwane Metropolitan City, are Tshivenda and Xitsonga, and Sepedi, Setswana, Tshivenda, Xitsonga, and isiNdebele, respectively. But, since the provincial languages depicted above only reflect *main* languages and not *minority* languages, it is difficult and dangerous for one to use anecdotal and speculative information in lieu of the one provided by the specified official government agencies. Now, if this is the case, are these sets of provincial language contexts—six sets of provincial trilingualism, two sets of provincial quadrilingualism, and one set of provincial bilingualism—what we refer to as South Africa’s multilingualism? Or, maybe it is the case of multilingualism being reduced to bilingualism, to trilingualism, or to quadrilingualism, depending on the province in which one finds oneself. Of course, it is not uncommon, at times, for multilingualism to be equated with bilingualism (cf. Alonso & Le, 2020; García, 2009; Surrain & Luk, 2017).

Indeed, it may also be the case that African language speakers’ (learners’) demographics at different provincial schools, especially in Gauteng’s Johannesburg and Tshwane metropolitan cities, reflect wider multilingual spectrums than the province’s main language spectrum. Then, if this is so, we should be talking about Gauteng’s school-based multilingualism as it applies to certain schools as opposed to a country-wide multilingualism that is often foregrounded. Even if that were to be the case, we do not know how many of such schools there are and what multilingual break-downs they have. All of this leads to this moot point: in what way do we talk of translanguaging in a mainly bilingual province such as Northern Cape? Translanguaging between two

languages, one of which is Afrikaans? In a similar but different way, the same applies to Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, and Western Cape. Here, translanguaging has to involve one majority African language and Afrikaans and English, if the main provincial languages portrayed above are anything to go by. All of the factors highlighted above tend to point to some sociolinguistic misrepresentations when it comes to multilingualism and translanguaging in South Africa. A key sociolinguistic question to ask, in this regard, is whether, in the South African context, it is possible to translanguage without multilingualism, something similar to what, in a different context, Sabino (2018) refers to as “theorizing languaging without languages” (p. 122). This view challenges sociolinguistic conventionalism about languages. Nonetheless, it is a moot point as to how and to what extent it may be applicable to South Africa: *translanguaging without multilingualism* or, to slightly tweak Sabino (2018) mainline phrase, *translanguaging without languages*? Or, to take this point further: *multilanguaging without languages*? (see Chaka, 2023a).

Lastly, at the core of South Africa’s touted multilingualism is individual multilingualism. This relates to full multilingualism (and here I am referring to all the eleven official languages) and a full-scale multilingual fluency any South African can have and display at any given time in different sociolinguistic contexts. Let us take Gauteng as a classic vortex of South Africa’s multilingualism. We do not know how many fully multilingual individuals there are in Gauteng, let alone in other provinces if ever they do exist. Neither do we know the fluency levels of their multilingualism in the languages in which they may claim to be multilingual. This is a conundrum of South Africa’s multilingualism that cannot be resolved easily or very soon as, to the best of my knowledge, Stats SA, an agency tasked with South Africa’s population census and population estimates, does not collect data on individual multilingualism. However, even if it did, because it employs surveys as its major data gathering instruments, the data it would have on individual multilingualism would not be that much accurate, but rather estimative. The point is, individual multilingualism is not a mechanical and straightforward property that individuals can claim to have by filling out surveys. Rather, it is a linguistic property that such individuals should display by fluently speaking different languages, and in the case of South Africa, by fluently speaking the eleven official languages at any given time. As such, it is not a statistical estimation variable like other language variables as it embodies a linguistic property of fluency, which is best demonstrated in real-world spoken and written language contexts than by simply claiming to have it on a survey form. The lack of clarity about individual multilingualism in South Africa serves as another instance of a sociolinguistic misrepresentation about South Africa’s much-vaunted multilingualism.

4. Conclusion

This paper has explored, a tenuous nexus between diversity, equity, social justice, and language activism as it relates to both multilingualism and translanguaging. Firstly, it has characterised a distinction between Euro-American multilingualism and translanguaging and multilingualism and translanguaging as they apply to the Souths. In this case, it has explicated its notion of the *Souths*. In addition, it has pointed out that multilingualism and translanguaging do not refer to the same sociolinguistic practice. To this end, it has argued that even though translanguaging tends to be framed differently from multilingualism, the latter, nonetheless, serves as its alter ego, its point of reference, and its nemesis.

Secondly, pertaining to multilingualism and translanguaging as vehicles of diversity, equity, and social justice, the paper has argued how efforts intended to realise these composite human rights-centric goals are confined mainly to school and university environments. In this context, it has opined that there is an apparent indifference to, and a lack of language activism for, multilingualism and translanguaging among some of university managers and planners. Given this, the paper has contended that multilingualism and translanguaging as transformative efforts are inherently constrained and hamstrung in giving effect to linguistic diversity, equity, and justice, and in challenging and unhinging the hegemony of English or Anglonormativity in South Africa. Rather, doing so requires dismantling current coloniallingual practices and structural colonialist or neocolonial tendencies prevalent in South Africa in which the government is complicit.

Thirdly, the paper has unpacked the myth about multilingualism and translanguaging prevailing in South Africa, which is often left unchallenged. One element of this myth is the reference to South Africa as a multilingual country, when none of its provinces has more than four main provincial languages from the pool of the eleven official languages. A country's multilingualism cannot exist outside of the aggregate languages its provinces have. Anything to the contrary is nothing short of a sociolinguistic misrepresentation. Fourthly and finally, the paper has highlighted the conundrum of South Africa's multilingualism, whose individual multilingualism together with its full individual multilingual fluency is an unknown and moot point.

Notes:

1. For more on relevant topics including activism, diversity, decolonisation epistemologies, multilingualism, translanguaging, equity, social justice, and other relevant (socio)educational topics, please see Balosa (2024),

Hannaford and Alexander (2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marias (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Xu and Fang (2024).

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